

STUDENT LEARNING, MONITORING AND INFLUENCE

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Abstract: This article provides information on how to influence students by studying them, how to conduct student learning in a planned and regular way, and how the class leader should have a description of the students in the class. given.

Key words: Head of class, teacher, group of students, parents, class activists, composition of parents' council.

If the head of the class does not know his students, he can make big mistakes in approaching students and choosing methods of pedagogical influence. For this reason, it is necessary for the head of the class to know the personality of the students, as well as the internal environment of the team. In this case, it is always necessary to take into account the individual characteristics of students, an individual approach to students is not an individual adaptation to the characteristics of each student. First of all, this is to actively search for a more effective way to have an educational impact on each student, taking into account the individual characteristics and personal experience of each student. An individual approach to students in the process of education consists of taking each student into consideration, knowing his characteristics, relying on his positive qualities, regularly helping him in difficult situations and encouraging him to behave well. - is to encourage for actions.

Studying students and exerting an educational influence on them, studying the student is not the final goal, but a necessary condition for providing them with education. The work of studying students is organically combined with the natural active participation of personality development, formation of necessary spiritual

qualities and character in students. The head of the class "projects" the development of positive qualities in the students' behavior and the elimination of negative qualities.

It is necessary to conduct students' learning in a planned and regular manner. It is necessary to study not isolated and random events in the student's behavior, but typical features that are very common in his personality. It should be taken into account that students are always growing and at the same time their interests are constantly changing. That is why it is necessary to teach students only to develop.

Learning students in the conditions of natural life and work. In the process of education, the student should be involved in socially useful counseling and community work. It is necessary to study the relations of students with the teacher, the school community, parents and others. In the process of this relationship, the person opens up more fully. Various methods and techniques can be used in learning. Conversation processes with parents also help the child learn.

Getting to know the students and their life and living conditions. Moral qualities of students, their achievements and shortcomings, home conditions and external environment during education are also taken into account.

It is necessary to study the whole personality of a person, not a specific feature. The head of the class can focus on learning some aspects of the student's behavior at different stages of educational work. In order to achieve comprehensive education of the student, it is necessary to plan the program well in advance, choose the plan of teaching the students, interview questions, essay topics. The head of the class should have the following description of the students of the class:

1. In class 1, there are total... students, ... one girl, one boy
2. one of them is a member of the "children and teenagers" association.
3. the number of excellent and poor students according to the rating of the control of students' knowledge levels
4. national composition

5. The place of classes among parallel classes
6. student's place of residence
7. class activists
8. composition of the parents' council
9. Students without parents
10. list of students in need of assistance
11. Providing students with textbooks
12. the number of members of the school library.

This is the initial work of the head of the class in the study of students and the information he collects. Also, the head of the class should know where the student's parents are, who they work for, what is the structure of the family, what is its cultural level, mutual relations in the family, the uniqueness of helping the child in the family, the routine of the child at home and the household situation. , the child's participation in household and community work, his friends and acquaintances outside of school, where the student will be on vacation, the most important events in the child's life, the state of the student's health, according to the information of these employees.

The group of students is an independent organization, but it needs pedagogical guidance. It is impossible to leave the students to their own devices, and at the same time to take the path of administration and command over the children's team. In the first case, the head of the class completely avoids these activities and allows the communication with the students to weaken, in the second case, he takes the path of oppression and destroys the independence of the students. The main task of the head of the class is to skillfully manage the activities of the children's team, to develop the initiative of students, to form the activity and independence of the class team.

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